

N-Benzoyl Migration and its Hydrolysis in presence of Poly-phosphoric Acid

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N-Benzoyl migration is observed in case of benzanilide and *o*-benzoyl toluidide in *p*-position, but in case of *p*-benzoyl-toluidide in ortho-position.

It has been reported in the earlier communication that acyl migration takes place exclusively in para-position to the amino group with acetanilide, *o*-acetotoluidide and *m*-acetotoluidide when heated with poly-phosphoric acid ; it was found convenient to isolate the resulting *p*-amino ketones as their acetyl derivatives from the intractable resinous reaction mass.¹

In the present work benzanilide, *o*-benzoyl toluidide and *p*-benzoyl toluidide were separately treated with PPA at 160-170° for 3½ to 4 hrs and it has been found that the benzoyl group migrates to para-position with respect to the amino-group in case of benzanilide and *o*-benzoyl toluidide ; whereas with *p*-benzoyl toluidide, in which the para-position is blocked, the migration takes place in the ortho-position. Further, it has been observed that the hydrolysis of the anilides also takes place yielding benzoic acid and the respective amines. At the top of the reaction flask, free benzoic acid produced during hydrolysis was found to collect due to sublimation.

It has been found convenient to isolate benzoic acid and the amino ketone together from the aqueous acidic reaction mixture by means of ethylacetate extraction and then to separate benzoic acid from the ester extract by means of aqueous sodium hydroxide. The phosphoric acid solution was then neutralised by means of sodium and ammonium hydroxide and the amine, set free, was extracted with ethylacetate. Both the amines and the amino ketones were isolated in pure condition as their acetyl derivatives.

However in case of *p*-benzoyl toluidide (I), the amino ketone of the reaction mass, when refluxed with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate, gave 2-hydroxy-4-phenyl-6-methyl quinoline (IV), thereby indicating that the benzoyl group must have migrated to the ortho position giving 3-methyl-6-amino benzophenone (II) and its acetyl derivative (III) cyclised to the 2-hydroxy quinoline in presence of the excess of the anhydride as shown here.

The formation of 4-hydroxyquinolines from acetoacetanilides and benzoylacetanilides in presence of PPA has been suggested in three alternative ways :

- (i) The interconvertibility of the anilide into the crotonate in the experimental conditions,²

1. Kusum Desai and C. M. Desai ; *Indian J. Appl. Chem. (Communicated)*

2. J. R. Houser and G. A. Reynolds ; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 2402 ; Kusum Desai and C.M. Desai ; *Indian J. Chem.* ; 1967, **5**, 170.

- (ii) The anilide undergoing a Fries type rearrangement,³
 (iii) The hydrolysis of the anilide leading to the formation of the intermediate ani-lanilide⁴,

The present work indicates that the reaction takes both the courses—the Fries migration and the hydrolysis of the anilide,—when anilides are heated with PPA; it may be that one or the other course preponderates depending on the nature of the anilide. In case of acetanilide, aniline, if produced by hydrolysis, could not be isolated as acetanilide from the reaction mass; but instead, an infusible mass was obtained. With benzanilide, when it was heated with increasing proportion of PPA, aniline as acetanilide was obtained from the reaction mass in decreasing proportion and when the PPA proportion was doubled, no acetanilide could be isolated; whereas instead, infusible white mass was obtained from the reaction mass after acetylation; at the same time, benzoic acid proportion was not found to decrease, thereby indicating that aniline, formed due to hydrolysis, might have condensed with the ketone forming white gelatinous infusible mass in presence of excess of PPA.

EXPERIMENTAL

(A) *Benzoyl migration and hydrolysis in benzanilide*: The reaction mixture of benzanilide (10 gm) and PPA [from 30 gm P_2O_5 in 18 ml of phosphoric acid ($d = 1.7$)] was heated at 160-170° for 4 hrs. The cold aqueous reaction mixture was extracted with ethylacetate; from the ester extract benzoic acid (1.295 gm) was separated by means of sodium hydroxide and hydrochloric acid. Mixed m.p. (121°) with the authentic specimen was not depressed.

p-Acetamino benzophenone: After the removal of ethylacetate from the ester extract, the residual mass was refluxed with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate for 3 hrs. The

3. B. Staskun and S. S. Israelstam; *J. Org. Chem.*; 1961, **26**, 3191.

4. A. K. Mallams and S. S. Israelstam; *ibid*; 1964, **29**, 3548.

aqueous solution was neutralised with ammonium hydroxide and the greasy precipitate was repeatedly crystallised from aqueous alcohol. The product (4.17 gm) was found to be *p*-acetamino benzophenone ; as its m.p. (153°) and mixed m.p. with the authentic specimen prepared from *p*-aminobenzophenone and acetyl chloride was found to be the same 153°.

p-Amino benzophenone : The above ketone was hydrolysed with 33 per cent alcoholic hydrochloric acid by heating it on steam bath for 1½ hr. and then neutralised with ammonium hydroxide. The precipitate was recrystallised from aqueous alcohol (m.p. 123-124°). Its mixed m.p. with the authentic specimen prepared from aniline and benzoyl chloride in presence of zinc chloride⁵ remained undepressed.

Acetanilide : The aqueous phosphoric acid solution was neutralised with sodium hydroxide and then finally ammonium hydroxide ; when the aniline separated was extracted with ethylacetate. The extract was acetylated with acetic anhydride, when the product (yield 1.12 gm, m.p. 114°) identical with acetanilide was obtained.

(B) *Benzoyl migration and hydrolysis in o*-benzoyl toluidide : The reaction mixture of *o*-benzoyl toluidide (10 gm) and PPA (pentoxide 30 gm and acid 18 ml) was heated at 160-170° for 3½ hr.

Benzoic acid (1.76 gm) and *o*-toluidine as *o*-acetotoluidide (0.93 gm) were obtained by the treatment as has been shown in experiment (A).

4-Acetamino-3-methyl-benzophenone and 4-Amino-3-methyl-benzophenone : After the removal of benzoic acid from the ester extract, the residual mass was refluxed with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate for 3 hr. The aqueous solution was neutralised with ammonium hydroxide when the greasy precipitate was obtained. From this mass, one portion sparingly soluble in aqueous alcohol (m.p. 175°, 1.290 gm) and the other portion (m.p. 124-130°) freely soluble were obtained.

The product (m.p. 175°) was found to be identical with 4-acetamino-3-methyl-benzophenone (m.p. 175°) ; as its mixed m.p. with the authentic specimen prepared by acetylation of 4-amino-3-methyl benzophenone remained undepressed.

The product (m.p. 124-130°) was hydrolysed with 33 per cent hydrochloric acid, and the solution was neutralised ; the precipitate was recrystallised from aqueous alcohol (m.p. 112°, 0.44 gm). This substance was identified as 4-amino-3-methyl benzophenone; as its mixed m.p. with the authentic specimen prepared from *o*-toluidine and benzoyl chloride⁶, remained undepressed.

(C) *Benzoyl migration and hydrolysis in p*-benzoyl toluidide : The reaction mixture of *p*-benzoyl toluidide (10 gm) and PPA (from 30 gm P₂O₅ in 18 ml acid) was heated at 160-170° for 4 hr.

Benzoic acid (1.25 gm) and *p*-aceto toluidide (1.17 gm) were isolated by the treatment as has been shown in experiment (A).

5. F. D. Chattaway ; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 85, 394.

6. F. D. Chattaway and W. H. Lewis ; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 85, 590.

After the removal of benzoic acid from the ester extract, the residual mass was refluxed with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate for 3 hr. The aqueous solution was then neutralised with ammonium hydroxide. From the greasy precipitate, after repeated crystallisation from water and 50 per cent alcohol, two products respectively with sharp m.p. were obtained; one with m.p. (148°, 1.27 gm) was identified as *p*-aceto toluidide and the other with m.p. 243° (0.610 gm) was identified as 2-hydroxy-4-phenyl-6-methyl quinoline, as its mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen obtained by cyclisation of *p*-benzoyl aceto toluidide³ remained undepressed.

The authors are grateful to the college authority for giving facilities for this work.

Further work along these lines is in progress.

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Received April 13, 1970.